

PHOTODEGRADATION OF ORGANIC SUBSTANCES USING PHOTOCATALYSTS

Sultonov Kamoliddin Norbo'ta

Jizzakh State Pedagogical University

kamoliddinsultonov007@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11259867>

Abstract: In this review article, the photodegradation and properties of various harmful organic substances using titanium dioxide are studied and analyzed.

Keywords: titanium dioxide, phenol photodegradation, methylene blue, sol-gel, photocatalyst,

Degradation of organic matter using photocatalysts

The most important task in the 21st century is to fight against the ever-increasing pollution of the environment. Today, the world is in a cancer of environmental pollution in one form or another, water pollution being the first of them. The chemical industry plays an important role in human civilization, but extensive anthropogenic and industrial activities have introduced large amounts of chemicals into the environment that are potentially harmful to many ecosystems. Among all other pollutants, dyes, pesticides, surfactants, chloro-organics, etc. are important classes of water pollutants and become a major source of environmental pollution. Nowadays, a lot of research is focused on wastewater treatment. Due to the complexity and variety of organic compounds used, it has been difficult to find a unique treatment method that fully covers the effective removal of all types of organic pollutants. Physical methods such as flocculation, reverse osmosis and adsorption on activated carbon are nondestructive and only transfer pollutants to other environments; thus causing secondary pollution [1]. Heterogeneous semiconductor photocatalysis [2, 3] has been widely studied and is considered a promising approach for the degradation of large amounts of organic pollutants because it is also economically efficient. Photocatalysis finds good opportunities in the field of creating renewable energy sources, as well as for cleaning the environment. Semiconductor-based photocatalysis has been extensively studied and shown to be a cleanup process for environmental protection [4-5]. Heterogeneous photocatalysis is part of advanced oxidation processes (AOP) and is a process with great potential for pollutant degradation and wastewater treatment [6-7].

Hydrocarbons. TiO_2 hydrocarbons (in the form of anatase) are used as photocatalysts in heptane oxidation [8]. Photocatalytic hydroxylation of an

aromatic ring using water as an oxidant in the presence of platinum-loaded TiO_2 [9]. The use of supported TiO_2 catalyst has attracted more and more attention of chemists in recent years due to its potential application in photocatalytic degradation of organic pollutants in water and air. It has also been reported that the use of adsorbents as a support for TiO_2 provides a good environment for the removal or degradation of target substances [10-11]. Tang

Phenol photodegradation

Recently, several technologies such as adsorption and biological processes have been used to effectively remove phenol. At the same time, the quality of wastewater is making more and more stringent requirements to achieve environmental protection. In addition, technologies such as

adsorption and coagulation can only transfer pollutants to other phases and cannot completely eliminate them. Other methods such as sedimentation, filtration, chemical and membrane technologies have high operating costs and/or generate secondary toxic pollutants during the treatment process; for example, byproducts of chlorination are mutagenic and carcinogenic compounds. In addition, the aforementioned methods have not yet demonstrated sufficient efficiency to meet quality criteria and generate non-biodegradable organic pollutants that appear in wastewater over time. Therefore, it is an alternative to solve these problems

methods are required. Recently, advanced oxidation processes (AOPs) are optimal alternative methods that have received much attention for phenol removal. Although AOPs contain different types of reaction systems, they all follow the same principle, namely oxidation processes based on the use of hydroxyl radicals as an oxidizing species to destroy pollutants present in water. Among AOPs, heterogeneous photocatalysis using semiconductor catalysts has demonstrated the efficiency of breaking down organic compounds into easily biodegradable molecules that can be mineralized into carbon dioxide and water. The basic principle of photocatalysis is that catalysts are excited by UV light and the resulting electrons and holes react with oxygen and/or water to form highly oxidizing free radicals such as OH. The pollutants in the water are then broken down by hydroxyl radicals into carbon dioxide and water forms. The type of

semiconductor catalyst used plays an important role in the efficiency of the photocatalytic process. TiO_2 , ZnO , Fe_2O_3 , CdS , GaP , and ZnS are semiconductor catalysts that are often used in photocatalytic processing. Among them, titanium dioxide (TiO_2) is widely used due to its photocorrosive and non-toxic nature, strong oxidation ability and high chemical stability. In addition, TiO_2 has also been shown to be the most active catalyst in previous studies. The efficiency of photocatalysis for the degradation of phenol has been widely studied. Many studies have shown that phenol can be decomposed into carbon dioxide and water. In addition, some of the intermediates formed in the photodegradation of phenol were found to be hydroquinone, resorcinol, and catechol (major byproducts), along with other aliphatic and acidic compounds. Based on the byproducts formed, general photodegradation pathways of phenol have been proposed by others. However, the intermediate products formed during the photocatalytic process, especially when using commercial TiO_2 , are still not sufficiently accurate. In addition, the precise identification of intermediate products, as well as the photodegradation pathways of phenol, are useful for studying the degradation of its derivatives. Heterogeneous photocatalysis, which is one of the advanced oxidation processes, allows the general degradation (mineralization) of the most toxic organic molecules in aqueous solution in the presence of a catalyst. These processes are based on the formation of hydroxyl radicals HO (Okamoto et al. 1985; Serpone, 1996) [4]. This species is a strong oxidizing agent due to its high reactivity. It is unstable and must be continuously produced in situ through chemical or photochemical reactions (Andreozzi et al., 1999; Chiron et al., 2000; Galze et al., 1992 [12]; Safarzadeh Amiri et al., 1996). Heterogeneous photocatalysis is based on a semiconductor used as a catalyst, which is activated by ultraviolet light. The anatase form of titanium dioxide is mainly used as a catalyst due to its high activity. The photocatalytic process involves the excitation of titanium dioxide with ultraviolet rays at a wavelength of 1 and 400 nm, and electron-hole pairs are formed.

are formed through the hole that can break down organic power. impurities present in wastewater. The oxygen supplied from the air (the system is mixed) cleans the electron produced by dissolution, receiving the recombination of electrons and electrons.

Photodegradation of methylene blue

Nowadays, a lot of research is focused on wastewater treatment. Due to the complexity and variety of organic compounds used, it has been difficult to find a unique treatment method that fully covers the effective removal of all types of

organic pollutants. The disposal of non-biodegradable organic chemicals is an important environmental problem. Dyes are an important class of synthetic organic compounds used in the textile industry, and therefore, a common industrial pollutant should be shifted to the visible region. 360 - Due to the persistence of modern dyes, traditional biological treatment methods for industrial wastewater are ineffective and often result in intensively colored discharges from treatment plants. Heterogeneous photocatalysis of the global environment through semiconductor particles

is a promising technology for pollutant reduction. Inorganic photocatalysts such as TiO_2 have been shown to be a relatively cheap and effective method of removing organic compounds and pollutant gases (Dalton et al., 2001) [16],

oxidation processes with TiO_2 photocatalysts have been shown to be an effective alternative (Malato et al. 2000 ; Marinas et al., 2001; Konstanou and Albanis, 2004) [17] absorb a small part of the solar spectrum of TiO_2 (3.2 eV). Thus, for maximum solar energy harvesting, light excitation of the TiO_2 semiconductor under wavelengths up to 380 nm generates electrons and holes in the conduction and valence bands, respectively. Dye sensitization reported for the degradation of colorants in dye-modified TiO_2 dispersions illuminated with visible light can also be used to degrade colorless water-pollutants (Chatterjee and Mahata, 2001; Chatterjee, 2004) [76] Several studies have recently been conducted. The case of heterogeneous photocatalytic degradation of paint under the influence of UV - A or visible light (Oliveira - Campos, 2003; Konstantinou and Albanis, 2004; Gomez et al., 2000; [18] Peralta - Zamora et al. 1998 ; Alaton et al., 2002) [19]. The oxidation process also decolorizes and mineralizes many types of azo dyes on a bench scale using artificial radiation (Goncl-).

associated with photocatalytic ($\text{TiO}_2/h\nu$) degradation to throw. Tungsten halogen, fluorescent light and sunlight were used as sources of radiation. Using sunlight as a source of UV energy is environmentally beneficial. Dependence of the rate of photooxidation of the dye on the following parameters: initial concentration of the dye; radiation time; radiation intensity was also

investigated. In the presence of metal ions, the efficiency of photocatalytic reactions can be increased by separating charge carriers and improving the rate of oxygen reduction.

TiO₂ nanocrystals have attracted much attention due to their photocatalytic activity. Previously, researchers studied the photocatalytic properties of water on the TiO₂ electrode under ultraviolet light, many synthesis methods for the preparation of TiO₂ nanoparticles, and their application in the environmental and energy fields, mainly in hydrogen storage, water separation, and photovoltaics. In recent years, fine nanoparticles of TiO₂ have attracted much attention due to their unique properties as light material, solar cell, and superior semiconductor as photocatalyst for photolysis and bactericidal action of water and organic compounds. This review reviewed the photodegradation properties of phenol using TiO₂ nanocomposites.

References:

1. C. Belvar, R. Bellod, A. Fuerte, MF Garcia, Nitrogen-containing TiO₂ photocatalysts: Part 1. Synthesis and solid characterization, // Journal of Appl. Catal. B: Environ., - 2006. - #65. - P.301-308.
2. AL Linsebigler, G. Lu, JT Yates, Photocatalysis on TiO₂ surfaces: Principles, mechanisms, and selected results, // Journal of Chem. Revs., - 1995 - No. 95 - P. 735- 758.
3. N. Serpone, Brief introductory remarks on heterogeneous photocatalysis, // Journal of Solar Energy Mater. Solar Cells, - 1995 - No. 38 - P. 369-379.
4. SC Ameta, R. Ameta, J. Vardia, R. Ameta, Z. Ali, Photocatalysis: A Frontier of Photochemistry, // Journal of Indian Chem. Soc., - 1999.-T.76. - No. 6 - P. 281-287.
5. Y. Cho, W. Choi, Visible light-induced reactions of humic acids on TiO₂, // Journal of Photochem. Photobiol., - 2002. - No. 148-P.129-135.
6. SC Ameta, R. Chaudhary, R. Ameta, J. Vardia, Photocatalysis: A Promising technology for wastewater treatment, // Journal of Indian Chem. Soc., - 2003,- T.80 -#4. -P.257-265.
7. Y. Cho, W. Choi, CH Lee, T. Hyeon, HI Lee, Visible light-induced degradation of carbon tetrachloride on dye-sensitized TiO₂, // Journal of Environ. Sci. Technol., -2001. - No. 35. -P.966-970.
8. MN Chong, B. Jin, CWK Chow, C. Saint, Recent developments in photocatalytic water treatment technology: // Journal of Water Res.-2010. - #44 - P.2997-3027.
9. I. Bouzaida, C. Ferronato, JM Chovelon, ME Rammah, JM Herrmann, Heterogeneous photocatalytic degradation of the anthraquinonic dye, acid blue

- 25 (AB25):A kinetic approach, // Journal of Photochem. Photobiol .,- 2004 .- #168 -P.23-30.
10. J. Herrmann, F. Jansen, RA Van Santen (Eds.), Water treatment by heterogeneous photocatalysis, Catalysis Science Series, Vol. 1, Chapter 9, // Journal of Imperial College Press, London, -1999-P.171–194.
11. JM Hermann, Heterogeneous photocatalysis: Fundamentals and applications to the removal of various types of aqueous pollutants, // Journal of Catal. Today, -1999. - No. 53 – P.115-129.
12. J. Shang, Y. Du, Z. Hu, Photocatalytic oxidation of heptane in the gas-phase over TiO₂, // Journal of Chemosphere,- 2002 -N^o46.-P. 93-99.
13. H. Park, W. Choi, Photocatalytic conversion of benzene to phenol using modified TiO₂ and polyoxometalates, // Journal of Catal.Today,- 2005 -N^o101.- P. 291-297.
14. T. Torimoto, S. Ito, S. Kuwabata, H. Yoneyama, Effects of adsorbents used as supports for titanium dioxide loading on photocatalytic degradation of propyzamide, // Journal of Environ. Sci. Technol., - 1996 - No. 30 - P. 1275-1281
15. A. Tang, Y. Xiao, J. Ouyang, S. Nie, Preparation, photocatalytic activity of cuprous oxide nano-crystallites with different sizes, // Journal of . Alloys and Comp., - 2008 - No. 457 - P. 447-451.
16. C. Natarajan, G. Nogami, J. // Electrochem. Soc. -2006.-T.143.-No.1547
- 17 . M. R. Hoffmann , ST Martin, W. Choi, DW Bahnemann, Environmental Applications of Semiconductor Photocatalysis, // J.Chem. Rev.-1995.-T.95. - P. 69-96.
18. J. Sukhaser, A. Wold, YM Gao, K. Dwight, Photoassisted decomposition of salicylic acid on TiO₂ and Pd/TiO₂ films, // Journal of . Solid State Chem., - 1995- No. 119 -P.339-343.
19. S. Ogata , H. Iyetomi, K. Tsuruta, F. Shimojo, A. Nakano, RK Kalia, P. Vashishta, Role of atomic charge transfer on sintering of TiO₂ nanoparticles: Variable-charge molecular dynamics, // Journal of . Appl. Phys.-2000 - #88. -P.6011-6017.

